

PRINCIPLES OR FUNDAMENTALS OF THE DIDACTIC EDUCATIONAL PROCESS THROUGH THE TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *The present article aims to share the results obtained by the investigation of how the Developmental Didactics can help the organization of the teaching of Sociology aiming at promoting the full development of students in transition phase. It was carried out through a Didactic Formative Intervention, in higher education and constituted by adolescent students..*

Key words: *theoretical thinking, didactics of development, didactic methods, Cultural-historical theory, dialectical logic.*

Every period of human development is marked by some process of crisis. The adolescence stands out for its collection of relevant crises and the intensity of the development processes that are in action in this period. The threshold experience of crisis is also the experience of recognition that a subject has concerning the limits to his/hers ability in providing solution to problems and challenges. Furthermore, the crisis is a development factor because it represents a problem with a solution located in a superior level in relation to the knowledge already acquired and the abilities previously developed by the subject. Thus, to solve a crisis implies to reach a set of new knowledge and abilities, namely, to transform potential knowledge and abilities into real ones. Crisis is a distinct element that enables development and promotes the necessary reasons and interests for confrontation.

Solving a crisis by means of appropriation of new cognitive-social content and also by elaboration/transformation of mechanisms of conduct is a sign of development. The fundamental fuel for every development process lies in the subject's inherent reasons and interests. This means that there can be no ongoing development process without having, in its basis, the outbreak of new interests and/or the reorganization of old ones. In order to reach a potential learning and develop, one relies deeply on the existence of some kind of interest. Therefore, a phenomenon that marks the transitional period is the internalization of new interests. This is based upon the need of confrontation with a new pattern of social relationship the adolescent experiments in this stage. In other words, it is fitting that the teacher considers setting up an environment that offers the means for expanding and developing students' interests. The increased participation in social situations is dialectically related to the development of conceptual thinking, resulting in the expansion of the adolescent's interest for something beyond his/her immediate experience. This condition is positively transformed in an environment that supports good learning processes and that enables the development of new abilities and interests. The use of problematization stands out as a remarkable didactic instrument. In this third proposition, problematization holds its importance as long as it can be used as a motivational tool. Problem situations are created and organized by the teacher, and they offer the student an external method of internalizing and developing interest for the study and the appropriation of school knowledge. Problematizations must be organized in a way so as to make sure that students are capable of providing an adequate solution to challenges, by applying scientific and school knowledge. The development of consciousness as a superior psychological function has a social origin, linked to the development of perception, the formation of concepts and the conceptual thinking. Vygotsky demonstrates that

socialized language has a fundamental participation in the organization and formation of thought. By socializing their internal language, children simultaneously take conscience of their own thought and start to form verbal thinking. Afterwards, in the transitional stage, verbalized thinking plays a decisive role in developing logical thinking, by converting concrete reality to an object of knowledge. It must be noted that in both moments the process of consciousness development is intimately connected to the elaboration of thought in language. Every didactic strategy designed to require from the student the appropriation of knowledge from the verbal application of meanings and senses elaborated in the classroom enables the realization of thought. The development of intellectual abilities of an awareness of itself can only occur if the student recognizes the cultural heritage of his/her society and participates in its expression, by appropriation. The verbal elaboration of these meanings and senses is a safe way for appropriation. Didactic actions serving as guidelines for the Developmental Education The systematization of didactic principles has also permitted the systematization of five didactic actions that integrate them:

1. diagnosis as starting point and process of teaching-learning-development, problematization as a generator of contradiction;
2. propelling crisis and the emergence of interests, and being the driving force for the formation of concepts,
3. collective activity,
4. the patent consciousness in the intentional use of conceptual meanings and generalization as an objectification of the concept for itself.

The concept modifies the complete thinking system of an adolescent by equipping him/her with tools of in-depth knowledge and reality comprehension, as well as tools for self-comprehension. This is achieved by showing the student the logical

structures in action. The concept can be characterized as a phenomenon of thought, particularly because it has a generalized meaning. The student can develop the ability of intentional use by understanding his/her reality – that is, its generalization –, through the critical experience of recognition of his/her own limits, through facing problem situations and also through the awareness of concepts' meanings. The concept has already an existence by itself, independently of student's appropriation, but once it attains the superior ability of generalizing its meaning, it becomes an instrument of the student's thinking, achieving an existence for itself. By being able to generalize, the student extrapolates the limits of reproduction of a memorized meaning, becoming able to understand his/her reality and also the phenomenon he observes, mediated by scientific concepts. In general, these principles and didactic actions, although presented separately, constitute a set of practices that are deeply guided by the Cultural Historical Theory. They allow the successful establishment of a teacher's practice-theory unit with the aim of promoting students' learning and development.

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